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Abstract

WP4 aims to establish an interoperability layer between different repositories by developing a common semantic model. This model will serve as a foundation for integrating records from resources provided by the RIs partaking in the project, each one for its reference domain in the Social Science and Humanities (SSH) sector. A rigorous semantic framework and data pipeline will be created to standardize data assessment, enrichment, and transformation. This pipeline will facilitate the harmonization of data, enabling machine processing and analysis. Additionally, WP4 will support the mapping of existing formats and standards to the common model, providing practical guidance and a curated ontology for semi-automated data extraction and transformation. Deliverable 4.9 “Workflow and requirements to ensure interoperability for Humanities Resources” builds on the results reported in the Deliverable 4.13 “Common Semantic Framework (interim)” and reports a much more complex and complete description of: i) ensure compatibility of formats, standards, and solutions by mapping them to the common interoperability model; ii) create and share a practical crosswalk for the possible introduction of new resources. Furthermore, a glossary will be proposed that collects a selection of ontological classes that will be used to semiautomatically extract and transform the data from the various resources in a semi-automatic way; iii) support in format definition and transformations to activities in the Pilots to be developed in WP7.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

RI	Research Infrastructure (CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS or OPERAS, in this document)
H2IOSC	Humanities and Heritage Open Science Cloud
CC	Cloud Computing
SOA	Service-Oriented Architecture
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
CLARIN-IT	CLARIN Italian node (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure)
DARIAH-IT	DARIAH Italian node (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities)
E-RIHS	E-RIHS Italian node (European Heritage Science Research Infrastructure)
OPERAS	OPERAS Italian node (Open scholarly communication in the european research area for social sciences and humanities)
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
REST	Representational State Transfer
SOAP	Simple Object Access Protocol
API	Application Programming Interface
VM	Virtual Machine
OAS	OpenAPI Specification
SSO	Single sign-on

Introduction

Objectives

WP4 address the persistent challenges of managing humanistic and cultural heritage materials, which are often fragmented across diverse digital platforms, tools, and standards and standards, and hence exhibits common problems:

- heterogeneous formats and the resulting necessity to semantically align contents;
- lock-in due to obsolete platforms and systems;
- lack of a long-term sustainability plan.

By promoting interoperability and semantic alignment, this WP aims to enhance the accessibility, contextualization, and reusability of the resources. This will involve developing tools for thesauri and vocabulary management, based on the landscaping carried out in WP2 and the technological assessment provided by WP3. The common ontology developed in WP4 will be employed to map and model data, facilitating the integration of diverse resources. A standardized mapping schema will streamline the transformation process from original formats to a semantic format, ensuring consistency and enabling the incorporation of new resources.

By establishing a robust interoperability layer, this WP will strengthen collaboration between the participating RIs, enabling the shared exploitation of resources and creating a sustainable framework for future integration. The development of a comprehensive architecture for semantic support and workflow management will underpin these efforts, ensuring the long-term preservation and accessibility of cultural heritage.

State of the Art

H2IOSC is a pioneering project to create a collaborative cluster of European distributed research infrastructures involved in the humanities and cultural heritage sectors with operating nodes across Italy. The 4 infrastructures partaking to the Federation address different aspects of research in the SSH and CH fields and support different disciplines in their research activities. The added value of the cluster lies in the integration of the efforts carried on by these different perspectives in one ecosystem for research.

To demonstrate alignment effort in an actual use-case the 4 RIs agreed during the WP4 periodical meeting to provide a complete mapping of the object 'manuscript' from different points of view; to cite a trivial example, for some, such as DARIAH and CLARIN, external aspects, such as the text it contains, may be of greater importance, while for others, such as E-RIHS, internal elements, such as the chemical composition of the inks detected, may be of greater importance. From the subsequent application study it was decided that CLARIN would focus on the text and on linguistic implications, DARIAH would deepen the philological dimension, E-RIHS would provide the physical point of view on the object considering it from a material perspective, and OPERAS would concentrate on editions and open science implications.

In this diversity of attention, a commonality of concepts defines, even if only partially, the Common Semantic Framework (CSF) of H2IOSC (see D4.13).

To understand how this is happening, one must consider the domain ontologies that the various IRs have constructed based on the ms. object (see, D4.9-13). The ontologies were defined according to the classic scheme subject-property-object and, to better see the connections and points of contacts they were converted into graphs with tools such as webowl. Seen as graphs, there is a non-empty intersection between them, which is part of the shared project reference ontology, i.e. the CSF.

WP4 produced different versions of the semantic description of the Manuscripts, currently under definition within the context of H2IOSC, in both graphic and textual (and machine-readable) formats. All files are freely available for viewing and modification by members of the WP4 group.

Thus, the definition of these ontologies is a process that tends to stabilize as the project progresses: at the end of the year 2024, DARIAH, relying on the external provider 'GruppoMeta' for the development part, completed the first usable version of the domain ontology, comprising an internal and an external ms. description sheet, thanks to which the ms. can be subjected to a workflow of data ingestion, mapping, processing and triplication, guided by dedicated software, the MetaFAIR Ecosystem (MFE), developed within H2IOSC by the GruppoMeta.

At present, the MFE software is integrated within the first of DARIAH's two pilots, the Digital Philology Hub (DPH, produced in activity 7.3, will be discussed in more detail in the following sections), thus ensuring consistency, efficiency and uniformity within the project between pilots and CSF.

Nevertheless, the entire H2IOSC marketplace, developed within WP5, is designed, among other things, to expose IRs services catalogued on the basis of controlled vocabularies also afferent to the CSF, and as such shared across the federation, further promoting a policy based on FAIR principles, a basic feature of the entire project.

DEFINITION OF THE REFERENCE DOMAIN

DARIAH (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities) is a Research Infrastructure (RI) operating within the domain of the Digital Humanities, an interdisciplinary field that merges traditional humanities scholarship with digital tools and methodologies. This domain facilitates the exploration, analysis, and dissemination of human knowledge using computational techniques and digital resources. It serves a diverse community of researchers, including philologists, lexicographers, and linguists, who leverage digital technologies to enhance their inquiries into language, literature, culture, and history. By fostering collaboration across disciplines and promoting innovative approaches to data management and analysis, the DARIAH RI aims to expand the ways in which scholars engage with texts and artifacts, enriching our understanding of the human experience.

REQUIREMENTS AND PROCESSES FOR INTEROPERABILITY

State of the Art

In order to achieve the goal of correctly defining a first version of the ontology able to accommodate all the relevant features belonging to the “manuscript” object, we proceeded with collective discussion meetings, often coinciding with the bi-weekly updates dedicated to WP4, which were often attended also by experts from outside the H2IOSC project, such as Prof. Irene Ceccherini, associate of Paleography (M-STO/09) of the SAGAS Department of the University of Florence.

This joint work allowed the creation of an initial informal document, drafted as a spreadsheet, in which the ontology was described and gradually refined.

At the same time, the infrastructures belonging to the federation have carried out a similar work, focused on the objects of their competence, thus making it possible to start an effective discussion on the concrete definition of the Common Semantic Framework, i.e. all the ontology that is common among the various IRs, plus the necessary integrations.

Based on the initial definition of the DARIAH domain ontology, it was possible to proceed, on the one hand, with the start-up of the development of a service, metaFAIR ecosystem, capable of managing the entire chain of data cleaning, processing, mapping, modeling and ingestion, and, on the other hand, with the development of internal tools to automate the construction of an RDF format file containing the ontology, so that it can be effectively operational and manageable at the computational level.

Both the metaFAIR ecosystem and the automation tools, although they do not yet have all the planned functionality, are already under test.

Objectives

The primary objective of the interoperability model is to facilitate seamless integration and communication among diverse research infrastructures (RIs) participating in the project. This

is achieved through the establishment of a Common Semantic Framework, which aims to ensure that resources can be shared and understood across different domains. By defining clear semantic relationships, stakeholders can enhance collaboration and data exchange, ultimately driving forward the objectives of research in Social Sciences and Heritage Sciences.

Methodology

To achieve the outlined objectives, a systematic methodology has been adopted, encompassing several key components. First, a comprehensive collection of Domain Ontologies will be developed, capturing the unique scientific interests of each participating RI. This will be complemented by a shared top-level Ontology that encompasses broad, high-level concepts relevant to all shared resources. Furthermore, a list of services offered by each RI will be compiled, ensuring that these services adhere to specific requirements for interoperability. Additionally, a robust data translation tool will be implemented, allowing for the effective conversion of data between different Domain Ontologies when semantic overlap exists.

Proposed solutions

To operationalize this methodology, several solutions are proposed. Each RI is tasked with providing a semantic description of its data resources through Domain Ontologies, thereby enabling accurate representation of scientific objects pertinent to its research focus. The top-level Ontology will serve as a cohesive framework that links these individual contributions, fostering a unified understanding of shared concepts such as places, dates, and resource collections. A comprehensive list of services will be maintained, complete with OpenAPI Specifications (OAS) and user-friendly Manifest files, ensuring clarity and accessibility for all participants. Finally, the Data Translation Tool will facilitate the necessary transformations between various data formats, thereby promoting interoperability across the federation.

DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE SEMANTIC FRAMEWORK

General principles

The design and development of the Common Semantic Framework are guided by fundamental principles that emphasize clarity, flexibility, and usability. The framework must accommodate the diverse needs of the RIs while maintaining a coherent structure that promotes interoperability. By prioritizing the creation of Domain Ontologies and a shared top-level Ontology, the framework aims to establish a common language that can be utilized by all stakeholders, thus ensuring that data can be effectively communicated and understood.

Reference resources

In support of this framework, a variety of reference resources will be developed. Each RI will contribute its Domain Ontologies, which will serve as foundational elements within the semantic structure. These ontologies will be complemented by a top-level Ontology that synthesizes broad concepts applicable across the entire federation. The reference resources

will also include detailed documentation of services provided by each RI, alongside relevant technological specifications that outline the operational readiness of these services. This comprehensive approach will ensure that all resources are readily accessible and easily navigable for users.

Description of process

Data extraction

The data extraction process involves identifying and retrieving relevant information from various resources within the RIs. This process is critical for populating the Domain Ontologies with accurate and meaningful data. It typically entails a thorough analysis of existing datasets to determine pertinent data points, which will then be transformed into a format compatible with the semantic framework.

Data mapping

Following extraction, the data mapping process ensures that the extracted information aligns with the appropriate entities within the Domain Ontologies. This step is crucial for establishing semantic relationships and ensuring that data can be effectively integrated across different systems. The mapping will be guided by Semantic Manifests that delineate how specific elements of the data correspond to concepts within the ontologies.

Modeling

The final phase in this process is modeling, where the structured data is formalized within the framework of the ontologies. This involves creating a coherent representation of the data that reflects its semantic relationships and facilitates easy access and utilization. The modeling process will also include the validation of data formats to ensure compatibility with databases and other tools employed within the research infrastructures. This phase is vital for enabling the effective use of the data in various applications, thereby maximizing its value to the research community.

DESCRIPTION OF THE ONTOLOGY

Classes and relations

The following is a structured overview of the main classes, entities, subclasses and properties identified in the complex ontology of elements related to manuscripts and historical archives:

Main Classes, Aliases, and Descriptions

1. **Aggiunta** (Aliases: Insertion, Integration, Addition)
Represents any addition or insertion of content within the manuscript. Useful to identify additions made post-composition.
 - **Properties:** Description (a textual description of the addition).

2. **Annotazione** (Aliases: Marginal Note, Annotation)
Denotes notes or comments added on the manuscript, possibly in the margins, as interpretative or clarifying additions.
 3. **Architettura della pagina** (Aliases: Page Organization, Layout)
Describes the layout of the manuscript page, including writing style and spatial organization.
 - **Properties:** Description, Type of Writing.
 4. **Attività**
This represents a type of event associated with the creation, use, or conservation of the manuscript, often linked to people or institutions.
 - **Subclass of Event.**
1. **Bibliografia**
Refers to bibliographic references related to the manuscript, such as works where it is cited or analyzed.
 2. **Carta** (Alias: Sheet)
Denotes an individual sheet or piece of paper in the manuscript.
 - **Subclass of:** Sheet.
 - **Properties:** Pagination (for tracking individual pages within the manuscript), Page (as a component of the sheet).
 3. **Codice** (Aliases: Book, Volume)
Refers to a bound collection of pages or sheets, a comprehensive unit often equivalent to a book or volume.
 - **Subclass of:** Manuscript.
 - **Properties:** Fasciculation (division into sections), Binding.
1. **Consistenza** (Alias: Dimensions)
Indicates the physical size or extent of the manuscript.
 2. **Decorazione**
Any decorative feature within the manuscript, such as illuminations or ornamental designs.
 - **Subclass of:** Illustration.
 3. **Dimensioni** (Alias: Format)
Describes the physical dimensions of the manuscript, including measurements in width and length.
 - **Properties:** Width, Length, Measurement Unit.
11. **Evento***
Refers to events related to the manuscript's history, creation, or circulation.

- **Properties:** Description, Location, Time Period.

12. Fascicolazione

Defines the process of dividing the manuscript into fascicles or sections, often for organization or binding purposes.

13. Fascicolo

A segment or grouping within the manuscript.

- 🔍 **Properties:** Pagination, Size, Material Support.

14. Foglio Intero

Indicates a complete, uncut sheet in the manuscript.

- **Subclass of:** Sheet.

15. Illustrazione

Refers to illustrations or drawings in the manuscript.

- **Properties:** Represents (an Event, Object, or Person illustrated).

16. Lingua

The primary language or languages in which the manuscript content is written.

17. Luogo*

Describes the geographical location associated with the manuscript.

- 🔍 **Properties:** Coordinates, Denomination, Geographic Extension.

18. Mano

Refers to the individual scribes or hands that contributed to writing in the manuscript.

- **Properties:** Position within the manuscript, Date, Type of Writing.

19. Manoscritto

Represents the entire manuscript as a unified entity.

- **Properties:** Page Architecture, Author, Content, Date, Title, Conservation Status, Support Material.

20. Miniatura

A subclass of illustrations specifically for small, decorative images, often with vibrant colors.

21. Notazione musicale

Refers to any musical notation or scores found within the manuscript.

22. Numerazione

Defines the numbering of pages, sheets, or sections within the manuscript.

23. Origine

Denotes the origin or provenance of the manuscript.

- **Subclass of:** Provenance.

24. **Periodo***

Specifies the time period associated with the manuscript's events or use.

- **Properties:** Start Date, End Date.

25. **Persona***

Represents people associated with the manuscript, including authors, owners, and other significant figures.

- **Properties:** Name, Role, Gender, Associated Events, Life Period.

26. **Provenienza** (Alias: Manuscript Circulation)

Describes the manuscript's historical ownership and circulation.

- **Properties:** Entity, Owner (Person), Period.

27. **Rubrica**

Refers to a rubric, typically a heading or title for sections within the manuscript.

- **Properties:** Attribution, Genre.

28. **Segnatura**

The identifying alphanumeric code assigned to the manuscript by libraries or collections.

- **Properties:** Entity, Location, Period, Alphanumeric Identifier.

29. **Stato di conservazione** (Alias: Condition)

Indicates the current preservation state of the manuscript.

30. **Supporto**

Refers to the physical material or support used for the manuscript, such as parchment or paper.

- **Properties:** Material, Conservation State.

31. **Testo**

Represents the textual content of the manuscript.

- **Properties:** Edition, Explicit, Language, Illustration, Incipit, Part, Rubric, Title.

32. **Versificazione** (Alias: Meter)

Refers to the poetic structure within the manuscript.

- **Properties:** Number of Strophes, Verses, Metrical Scheme, Rhyme Scheme.

Additional Properties

- **Genere Testuale:** Refers to the literary genre of the text.
- **Incipit:** The opening line or passage of the text.
- **Tipo di Scrittura:** The type of script or handwriting style used.
- **Unità codicologica:** A codicological unit, meaning a distinct segment of the manuscript for analytical purposes.

- **Versi per strofa:** Number of lines per stanza, often relevant for poetic texts.

The case of the DARIAH RI will be used in this document to provide a specific realization of the ontology-related components of the Common Semantic Framework.

DARIAH has defined a single Domain Ontology, which describes in details **Manuscripts** from the twin point of view of the physical object and the information contained therein; in particular, the *internal description* of each Manuscript defines a set of *text objects* which are one of the main research interests for the DARIAH community of users.

In the [csf-utilities](#) repository, a DARIAH service is available with the specific aim of generating a formal ontology description in RDF/XML format from a straightforward worksheet-based description table.

Below is an example (in Italian) of a sample description table for a manuscript ontology:

Concetto	Contesto	esempio	Def.
Manoscritto Codice	Descrizione Esterna		LIBRO formato da FOGLI piegati in due (BIFOGLI) e riuniti in uno o più FASCICOLI, cuciti mediante un filo lungo la linea di PIEGATURA Nota: Il termine MANOSCRITIO indica, più generalmente, qualunque testo scritto a mano
Ttolo del codice	Descrizione Esterna	Codex Amiatinus	
Supporto	Descrizione Esterna	pergamena	Materiale sul quale è stata tracciata la scrittura o che è destinato a riceverla (MM)
Consistenza Dimensioni	Descrizione Esterna	I + 177 + II-III	Numero complessivo delle CARTE che costituiscono un VOLUME, indipendentemente dalla maniera in cui sono numerate (MM)
Volume	Descrizione Esterna		Unità costituita da una serie di BIFOGLI o di FOGLI ricoperti o destinati ad essere ricoperti da una sola LEGATURA, a prescindere dal fatto che si tratti di un insieme costituito da una o più UNITÀ CODICOLOGICHE, indipendente o parte di un'opera in più volumi
Bifoglio	Descrizione Esterna		Unità costitutiva del FASCICOLO, rappresentata da un pezzo rettangolare di PERGAME-NA, CARTA ... , piegato a metà per formare due CARTE

Appendix 1 shows the complete table

ENGLISH TRANSLATION:

Concept	Context	Example	Definition
Manuscript – Codex	External Description		A book made of sheets folded in half (<i>bifolia</i>) and gathered into one or more <i>quires</i> , sewn together with thread along the <i>fold</i> . Note: The term <i>manuscript</i> more generally refers to any text written by hand.
Title of the Codex	External Description	<i>Codex Amiatinus</i>	
Writing Surface	External Description	<i>Parchment</i>	The material upon which the writing has been inscribed or that is intended to receive writing (MM).
Extent – Dimensions	External Description	I + 177 + II–III	Total number of <i>leaves</i> (folios) that make up a <i>volume</i> , regardless of how they are numbered (MM).
Volume	External Description		A unit made up of a series of <i>bifolia</i> or <i>leaves</i> , bound or intended to be bound in a single <i>binding</i> , regardless of whether it consists of one or more <i>codicological units</i> , and whether it is a stand-alone piece or part of a multi-volume work.
Bifolium	External Description		A constituent unit of the <i>quire</i> , consisting of a rectangular piece of <i>parchment, paper, etc.</i> , folded in half to form two <i>leaves</i> .

A table of this kind must be complemented by a second table that defines the properties and relationships between the ontology's classes and entities. An extract from the table is shown below:

Subject	Property	Object
Codice	is composed by	Fascicolo
Codice	has	Legatura
Fascicolo	has	Consistenza
Fascicolo	has datation	Data
Luogo	has	Coordinate
Manoscritto	Is described by	Contenuto
Manoscritto	has datation	Data
Manoscritto	Is owned by	Ente
Manoscritto	is composed by	Foglio

Here follows an English translation of the above items:

Subject	Property	Object
Codex	is composed by	Quire
Codex	has	Binding
Quire	has	Collation
Quire	has datation	Date
Place	has	Coordinates
Manuscript	Is described by	Contents
Manuscript	has datation	Date
Manuscript	Is owned by	Insitution
Manuscript	is composed by	Sheets

Appendix 2 shows the complete table

The final [RDE](#), aligned with DARIAH's manuscript ontology for the H2IOSC project that is shown at the beginning of this paragraph, is versioned in the repository and will be updated as further developments in the ontology emerge.

In the case where the DARIAH domain ontology needs to be extended or modified, based on the previous section, it turns out that it is natural to update the ontology description contained in the spreadsheet at the outset, so as to have a human-readable framework of first instance. To get to an operational version of the ontology, it is necessary to translate the information from human-readable to machine-readable, so one can proceed with the DARIAH services previously mentioned and posted on the repository [csf-utilities](#).

To further facilitate the user in the first step of this workflow concerning the conversion of the spreadsheet into a YAML1 file, an additional DARIAH tool deposited on a repository [baltig](#), which serves as a GUI for a YAML editor- is under development.

On the other hand, from the point of view of the process of acquiring, processing, and loading data into the database, the tool developed by the company that won the relevant contract is

undergoing refinement. The tool is called metaFAIR ecosystem and has a web interface that can be reached at <https://dev-ovi-metafad.devworkbench.it/>.

The user of metaFAIR ecosystem will be able to populate the necessary fields of a form divided into several sections in order to upload the ontologically relevant data of the manuscript object, i.e., that which involves internal description and external description, to the infrastructure database.

In addition to the GUI, the metaFAIR ecosystem is also accessible via API, so as to make it interoperable at multiple levels: the easiest and most immediate example of this is the direct integration with the DPH. Indeed, in the DPH users have, already in the current development version, the possibility to upload manuscripts deposited on metaFAIR ecosystem.

USE CASES

Within WP7, task 7.3, the deployment of the DARIAH pilot called Digital Philology Hub (DPH) is planned.

The DPH is developed to eliminate technological and semantic barriers that limit the full utilization of innovative potential within domain-specific research infrastructures. This pilot is grounded in real research scenarios from various national and international projects and in the light of what has been reported so far in this document, we aim to expand it to ensure interoperability with resources created or managed by researchers from different disciplines yet focused on the same objects or contexts.

The DPH has been conceived, architected and is being built around a clear need of Philology in the Digital Humanities, which has been well outlined in the work “Filologia digitale del Medioevo italiano”²: to have a computer tool that assists the philologist in all the steps leading to the editing of a (digital) critical edition.

As is common practice, in order for such a tool to be truly effective, it is essential to have appropriate use cases. Through them, interactions between users and the system are outlined, detailing the steps required to achieve the desired outcome.

For the DPH, a *use case* describes a scenario where researchers use the hub to publish a digital critical edition, starting from the selection of manuscripts. Indeed, it involves the application of the DPH’s tools and resources to support tasks such as accessing, analysing, and also sharing philological data, facilitating collaboration across different disciplines and infrastructures.

For our specific purposes, we identified three works that are perfectly suited for the role of use cases for the DPH:

- “Volgarizzamento siglato III dell’Opus agriculturae di Palladio”
- “Rime di Guittone d’Arezzo”
- “Studio della tradizione del Fiore di virtù”

Respectively, they are examples of prose, poetry and prosimetrum of the ancient Italian.

DESCRIPTION OF THE PILOTS

The DPH has been designed to implement:

- An environment for depositing and displaying digital images of manuscripts.
- Procedures to support manuscript description.

- Innovative procedures and tools to facilitate transcription of manuscripts and printed texts (e.g., incunabula), including automatic or semi-automatic approaches based on AI, Deep Learning, and Machine Learning (supported by the DARIAH AI Hub in Naples).
- Software for processing manuscript images for use in critical editions (e.g., EVT-like and IIF).
- Software for the automatic or semi-automatic collation of variant witnesses, using advanced approaches based on AI, Deep Learning, and Machine Learning (supported by the DARIAH AI Hub in Naples).
- Software for lexicographic analysis of variants in early Italian texts.

The pilot develops ontologies and conducts research on the Semantic Web, using metadata from repositories and data from corpora. In the next paragraph we will see which repositories will be included in the first release of the DPH.

RESOURCES

In its first release, the Digital Philology Hub (DPH) integrates access to three key repositories—**Mirabileweb**, **e-codices**, and **Manus Online**—through a dedicated service called the **MetaFair Ecosystem**. This service, developed as part of the H2IOSC project, allows the DPH to directly call MetaFair’s APIs, making the resources from these repositories readily accessible to users in a unified environment.

Let’s briefly introduce these three repositories:

- **Mirabileweb**: A comprehensive digital library focused on medieval studies, providing a rich collection of manuscripts, bibliographic data, and scholarly research. It serves as an essential resource for researchers in philology, literature, and historical studies.
- **e-codices**: The Swiss digital library for manuscript studies, e-codices hosts high-quality digital images and metadata of medieval manuscripts preserved in Swiss libraries. It is widely used by scholars for accessing and studying rare and historic texts.
- **Manus Online**: An Italian database that catalogues a vast number of Italian manuscripts. It provides researchers with access to detailed descriptions and information about manuscripts held in Italian libraries, supporting various research efforts in historical and philological studies.

The MetaFair Ecosystem functions as a connective platform that enables DPH users to seamlessly access these repositories. By employing MetaFair’s APIs, the DPH can retrieve and display data from each repository, allowing researchers to conduct philological analysis, view manuscript images, and leverage metadata in a consolidated space. This integration enhances interoperability and data accessibility across different collections, fostering more efficient research in digital philology.

IMPLEMENTATION

The development of the DPH was outsourced to an external company, as per Annex C of the project, standing the condition that all the code will be open and accessible by the end of the project (31st of October 2025).

The DPH is in fact organised as a complex workflow, in which several possible paths are permissible to reach the critical edition. In each of the basic steps of this workflow a particular service is realised, in the entirety of which we include

- manuscript management,
- transcription,
- lemmatisation,
- collation,
- varia lectio,
- critical apparatus,
- glossary,
- commentary,
- critical text.

The production server is DARIAH's datacenter in Florence, and the technologies used for implementation are varied: in a microservices architecture encapsulated in docker containers, we find mariadb as open-source relational database, php for the backend and for the frontend with a laravel framework (blade), as well as typescript and js.

The work is fully versioned on GitLab, and periodic releases are accompanied by documentation.

Finally, all code must undergo a test phase, designed in advance, to ensure its robustness and reliability.

RESULTS

Among the above-mentioned services of which the DPH is composed, the priority in development is not constant, as some of them are not indispensable in the drafting of a critical edition, while others are.

With this in mind, a functional form of the DPH of minimum value can be defined, which responds to the logic of Minimum Viable Platform (MVP), which we intend to achieve before the end of the project, more precisely by the end of 2024.

In the MVP version of the DPH, we only see the following services implemented:

- manuscript management,
- transcriptions,
- collation,
- varia lectio
- critical apparatus,
- critical text.

To date, the manuscript and transcription management services are completed, while the collation service is currently in the validation phase.

Lower development impact services such as varia lectio, critical apparatus and critical text will be completed by 2024.

In the following months, until the end of the project, the DPH will be gradually enriched with all the additional services not included in the MVP, making it more versatile, high-performant and responsive to the needs of the public.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

Deliverable 4.9 has illustrated the intermediate achievements and methodological foundations set by WP4 to ensure interoperability of DARIAH-IT resources within the H2IOSC federation. Through the definition of a Common Semantic Framework (CSF), the alignment of diverse ontologies, and the deployment of concrete tools like the MetaFAIR Ecosystem and Digital Philology Hub (DPH), the project has made significant strides in enabling cross-infrastructure resource integration.

Looking ahead, the evolution of WP4 will proceed along three principal axes. First, ontological refinement and modular expansion will be prioritized, ensuring the CSF remains responsive to emerging scholarly needs and new resource types. Second, technical maturation and scaling of the MetaFAIR and DPH systems will enable their integration into a broader range of pilots, including additional domains such as lexicography, material sciences, and art history. Third, sustainability and governance models will be articulated to guarantee long-term operability beyond the funding period, engaging institutional stakeholders and the wider SSH community.

Future work will also involve the formalization of feedback loops between the RI and the content providers, enabling agile evolution of workflows. Particular attention will be paid to the onboarding of new resources, where the guidelines developed in this deliverable will be tested and improved based on real-world integration cases. These efforts will collectively ensure that H2IOSC can act as a blueprint for future interoperable infrastructures in the humanities domain.

OPEN QUESTIONS

- How will emerging technological standards influence the existing Common Semantic Framework, and how flexible should the CSF be to accommodate these changes?
- What long-term governance structures should be implemented to maintain and update the interoperability model beyond the project's lifecycle?
- Which strategies can most effectively support the participation of external, non-project-related repositories to ensure comprehensive integration and collaboration?

GUIDELINES FOR ADDING NEW RESOURCES

1. **Resource Evaluation:** Assess the compatibility of new resources against the current semantic framework, identifying potential semantic gaps and overlaps.
2. **Ontology Mapping:** Develop a detailed semantic mapping between the resource-specific metadata standards and the CSF ontologies, creating clear crosswalk documentation.

3. **Implementation of Crosswalks:** Employ the MetaFAIR Ecosystem tools and API to automate data translation, ingestion, and integration.
4. **Validation and Quality Assurance:** Conduct rigorous testing using predefined validation procedures to ensure data integrity, semantic accuracy, and interoperability.
5. **Documentation and Sharing:** Provide comprehensive documentation of the integration process and crosswalk mappings, and make these openly accessible within the H2IOSC federation.
6. **Feedback and Revision:** Establish a feedback loop with the resource owners to refine and optimize semantic mappings and interoperability processes continually.

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APPENDIX 1

Concetto	Contesto	Esempi	Definizione
<p>Aggiunta Inserzione Integrazione Addizione</p>	Descrizione Interna	<p>c. 152r margine esterno: hic introitus dicitur etiam in solemnitate corporis Christi.</p> <p>c. 156v margine esterno: Introitus pro sanctissima trinitate quere in fine huius libri fo. 168.</p> <p>c. 163r margine esterno: Require clxxv cui fa seguito, di altra mano più tarda: in libro sanctorum in die purificationis S. Marie virginis.</p>	<p>Menzione iscritta al di fuori del CORPO DELLA PAGINA, destinata ad esservi introdotta durante la lettura o al momento di una COPIA ulteriore</p>
<p>Annotazione Chiosa Nota</p>	Descrizione Interna		<p>Breve testo di contenuto informativo, esplicativo o critico</p>
<p>Architettura della pagina Organizzazione della pagina Disposizione della pagina Utilizzazione della pagina Impaginazione</p>	Descrizione Esterna		<p>Disposizione generale dei diversi elementi che figurano su una PAGINA, nel rispetto di determinati canoni ed equilibri [M 331.01]</p>
Attività	Generale		
<p>Attribuzione in Rubrica</p>	Descrizione Interna		<p>Autore/i come attribuito nella rubrica del manoscritto, se presente</p>
Bibliografia	Storia	<p>Monti S., L'esposizione di arte sacra in Bellinzona (settembre, 1903), in „Bollettino Storico della Svizzera italiana“ 26 (1904), 17-18;</p> <p>[Respini G.], Il Ticino liberale-conservatore giudicato dalle sue opere, in „Bollettino Storico della Svizzera italiana“, 11 (1936), 87;</p>	
<p>Bifoglio Foglio</p>	Descrizione Esterna		<p>Unità costitutiva del FASCICOLO, rappresentata da un</p>

			pezzo rettangolare di PERGAME-NA, CARTA, ... , piegato a metà per formare due CARTE
Carta Foglio	Descrizione Esterna		Ciascuna delle due metà di un BIFOGGIO [Nota: Il termine FOGGIO viene da alcuni impiegato come sottomultiplo di BIFO-GLIO, per indicare la CARTA]
Cartulazione Cartolazione Cartulatura Cartolatura Foliotazione Foliazione	Descrizione Esterna		Cartulazione. Numerazione di tutte le CARTE che compongono un VOLUME, normalmente apposta sul RECTO di ciascuna
Circolazione del manoscritto	DUBBIO	A seguito della soppressione del convento di S. Francesco di Locarno, avvenuta nel 1848, il graduale (unitamente agli antifonari II, III e IV) fu probabilmente trasportato presso il convento della Madonna del Sasso di Orselina - affidato ai cappuccini - dove ricevette la segnatura „25-235 I“ (etichetta cartacea moderna originariamente applicata sull'asse anteriore, dopo il restauro conservata separatamente). Qui è presente sicuramente nel 1903, quando il Monti (Monti, 17) lo vide già privato di alcune miniature. A detta del Respini (Respini, 87) le prime manomissioni risalirebbero a prima del 1876, subito dopo la soppressione del convento. Successive asportazioni di miniature avvennero dopo il 1943 e dopo il 1967. Attualmente il graduale e gli antifonari II, III, IV appartiene allo Stato del Canton Ticino e si trovano in	

		deposito presso il convento dei cappuccini della Madonna del Sasso di Orselina.	
Consistenza Dimensioni	Descrizione Esterna	I + 177 + II-III	Numero complessivo delle CARTE che costituiscono un VOLUME, indipendentemente dalla maniera in cui sono numerate (MM)
Contenuto	Descrizione Interna	<p>Contiene i canti antifonali e responsoriali delle messe dall'Avvento alla domenica XXIII dopo la Pentecoste.</p> <p>2r-178v Proprium de Tempore [Dominica prima de adventu. L'inizio manca] 2r ... misericordiam tuam et salutare tuum da nobis. Offertorium. Ad te domine levavi animam meam >Dominica secunda de adventu. Introitus.< Populus Syon ...-... 178v Dominica XXIII post pentecosten officium resumitur de dominica preterita. Dicit dominus ego cogito et cetera.</p> <p>[mancano le cc. 20-21 con una parte dell'Ufficio per S. Stefano e l'intero ufficio per S. Giovanni Battista] Il testo segue l'Ordo Breviarii di Aimone da Faversham, ed. S. P. J. Van Dijk, Sources of the modern liturgy, The Ordinals by Haymo of Faversham and Related Documents, Leiden, II (1963), 207-270.</p> <p>123v-128r Litanie, da notare Francesco Antonio, Domenico, Clara. A c. 125v nel margine superiore aggiunti in un secondo momento i nomi di S. Abbondio e di S. Ludovico.</p>	

Decorazione	Descrizione Esterna	<p>iniziali ritoccate in giallo rubriche ed indicazioni liturgiche in rosso. Ovunque sono visibili, a penna marrone e di modulo molto piccolo, le indicazioni per il rubricatore e per i miniatori iniziali filigranate: piccole alternate rosse e blu all'inizio dei versetti medie all'inizio delle messe delle domeniche comuni e dei giorni feriali Queste iniziali filigranate sarebbero opera di un "Miniatore calligrafo" attivo anche nel codice III e IV (v. Hudig-Frey 1971 p. 302, 318; Gilardoni 1972, p. 228: „calligrafo delle filigrane“; Speroni 2000, 42 che però dice attivo nell'I, II e IV)</p>	<p>Disposizione generale dei diversi elementi che figurano su una PAGINA, nel rispetto di determinati canoni ed equilibri</p>
Edizione	Storia		
Explicit	Descrizione Interna		
Fascicolazione	Descrizione Esterna	<p>(IV-1)8 + IV16 + (IV-2)24 + 12 IV120 + V130 + IV138 + (IV-1)145 + (IV-1)154 + 3 IV178 + I180 + (II-2)182</p>	<p>a) Numero dei FASCICOLI che compongono un VOLUME o un'UNITÀ CODICOLOGICA e loro TIPO b) Studio del TIPO e della STRUTTURA dei fascicoli che compongono un volume o un'unità codicologica</p>
Fascicolo	Descrizione Esterna		<p>Serie di BIFOGLI inseriti l'uno dentro l'altro ed uniti o pronti per essere uniti da uno stesso passaggio del FILO DI CUCITURA. Il fascicolo può essere eventualmente composto da un un unico bifoglio, o anche da una singola CARTA, cucita autonoma-mente agli altri fascicoli</p>

Foglio	Descrizione Esterna		a) Superficie rettangolare di PERGAMENA, CARTA, ... (corrispondente ad un FOGLIO DI FORMA o ad una PELLE intera, o anche ad un loro sottomultiplo), come si presenta an-teriormente alle operazioni di PIEGATURA o di suddivisione eseguite per ottenere i BIFOGLI *b) Termine usato come sinonimo di BIFOGLIO *c) Termine usato come sinonimo di CARTA
Foglio Intero	Descrizione Esterna		Riferimento specifico al significato a) di Foglio
Dimensioni Formato	Descrizione Esterna	528 x 375 mm	Dimensioni (altezza e larghezza) del FOGLIO o della CARTA
Ente	Generale		
Evento	Generale		
Fondo	Storia		
Genere in Rubrica	Descrizione Interna		
Genere testuale	Descrizione Interna	Testo morale, Testo religioso...	
Illustrazione	Descrizione Interna		Rappresentazione di oggetti, personaggi, scene ... in rapporto con il testo
Incipit	Descrizione Interna		

Legatura	Descrizione Esterna		a) Operazione che consiste nel confezionare un LIBRO cucendo l'uno all'altro i FASCICOLI e aggiungendo eventualmente altri elementi (COPERTA, CAPITELLI, CARTE DI GUARDIA...) b) Risultato di tale operazione NOTA: In questo contesto siamo interessati al significato b)
Lingua	Descrizione Interna		
Luogo	Generale		
Luogo di conservazione	RELAZIONE!		Luogo in cui un LIBRO è attualmente conservato
Mano	Descrizione Esterna		
Manoscritto	Descrizione Esterna		Qualunque oggetto fisico che riporta testo scritto a mano
Codice Libro Volume	Descrizione Esterna		LIBRO formato da FOGLI piegati in due (BIFOGLI) e riuniti in uno o più FASCICOLI, cuciti mediante un filo lungo la linea di PIEGATURA
Marginalia	Descrizione Interna		Nota: Il termine MANOSCRITTO indica, più generalmente, qualunque testo scritto a mano
Miniatura	Descrizione Interna		Dipinto eseguito in un MANOSCRITTO, in particolare se si tratta di un'ILLUSTRAZIONE
Notazione musicale	Descrizione Interna	Notazione musicale quadrata a inchiostro nero su tetragramma a inchiostro rosso	
Numerazione	Descrizione Esterna		Numero d'ordine attribuito ai FASCICOLI, ai BIFOGLI, alle CARTE o

			alle PAGINE di un VOLUME
Numero strofe	Descrizione Interna		
Numero versi	Descrizione Interna		
Origine	Storia	<p>Si tratta probabilmente del primo di due volumi: il secondo avrebbe dovuto contenere il Proprium de sanctis, come fa pensare la presenza del richiamo a c. 180v In vigilia Santi Andree apostoli, ed il Commune sanctorum. Il testo segue lo schema del Libro ordinario di Aimone di Faversham (ed. S. P. J. Van Dijk, Sources of the modern liturgy, The Ordinals by Haymo of Faversham and Related Documents (1243-1307), Leiden, vol. II (1963).</p> <p>Gli elementi utili per la datazione del manoscritto ai primi decenni del XIV secolo sono:</p> <p>l'aggiunta nelle litanie, non molto dopo la stesura del testo, del nome di S. Ludovico, canonizzato nel 1297 (c. 125v).</p> <p>la Messa festiva "De sancta Trinitate" trascritta alla fine del Proprium de Tempore, autorizzata per l'ordine dal capitolo generale di Parigi del 1266 e nel 1316 estesa da papa Giovanni XXII a tutta la chiesa</p> <p>la annotazione tarda (XIX sec.) nel margine inferiore di c. 130v: Librum hunc accurate scripserunt Anno 1315 Fr. Jacobus domini Rostelli de Orello lector et beneficus alumnus cenobii et ecclesie S. Francisci de Locarno et fr. Joannes de Raimondis.</p> <p>lo stile delle iniziali miniate,</p>	Luogo in cui un LIBRO è stato approntato

		i cui esempi più vicini si trovano nella miniatura padovana della fine del sec. XIII e della prima metà del sec. XIV, quali per es. il Ms. 328 di probabile origine padovana con iniziali miniate che presentano il motivo dei draghetti, databile agli inizi del XIV sec. (v. G. Abate - G. Luisetto, Codici e manoscritti della Biblioteca Antoniana, Vicenza 1975, vol. 2, 607, fig. 46).	
Pagina	Descrizione Esterna		Ciascuna delle due superfici opposte di una CARTA [Nota: Impropropriamente, nella terminologia del libro moderno, il termine "pagi-na" è adoperato talvolta per indicare la CARTA]
Partizione	Descrizione Interna		Per testi in prosa
Periodo	Generale		
Persona	Generale		
Provenienza	Storia	Il graduale è sicuramente stato eseguito per un convento francescano e destinato poi al convento di S. Francesco di Locarno, come attesterebbe l'aggiunta nelle litanie del nome di S. Abbondio vescovo di Como, diocesi cui apparteneva all'epoca Locarno e cui il manoscritto era destinato, e l'annotazione del sec. XIX nel margine inferiore di c. 181r: Iste liber choralis iuris est conventus Sancti Francisci fratrum minorum conventualium de Locarno in tanta rerum vicissitudine aduc superstitis. Anno 1817. Non ha invece nessun	a) Indicazione degli antichi POSSESSORI O dei LUOGHI DI CONSERVAZIONE di un LIBRO b) [in particolare:] Ultimo possessore prima di quello attuale

		<p>valore l'ipotesi, più volte formulata dagli studiosi sulla base dello Statutum pro libris choralibus scribendis trascritto a c. 181, che il graduale sia stato prodotto in uno scriptorium di Locarno (Hudig-Frey, 300-301, Gilardoni 228; Speroni 2000/3, 18). Si tratta infatti di prescrizioni databili intorno alla metà del XIII sec. che i copisti avrebbero dovuto anteporre all'inizio del testo vero e proprio del graduale. L'editore van Dijk (vol. I, p. 120) ha reperito nove manoscritti, tutti di area italiana, che presentano questo testo all'inizio.</p> <p>Potrebbe invece essere verosimile l'ipotesi secondo la quale, come si legge a c. 182v, frate Giacomo di Rastelli Orelli, lettore del convento, e frate Giovanni Raimondi, si siano procurati il graduale - e probabilmente anche gli antifonari (codici II, III, IV) - per il convento nel 1315, in occasione di una nuova consacrazione della chiesa di S. Francesco, avvenuta nel 1316: ... Et mihi fratri Jacobo domini Rastelli de Orello lectori conventus minorum in Locarno ... tradidit personaliter fideliter ad perpetuam rei transcripsi. Et in hoc conventuali libro quem mo ccco xvo una cum fratre Johanne de Raymondis cum multa sollicitudinem fieri procuravimus notavi diligenter atque conscripsi. Suffragherebbero questa ipotesi anche le trascrizioni (c. 182v) alla fine del codice</p>	
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		della memoria concernente la costruzione di un armadio per la biblioteca del convento, della lettera di consacrazione del cimitero e di due altari avvenuta nel 1316, e della memoria di una donazione del 1315 per la costruzione di un pulpito e l'acquisto di un messale e di vari paramenti.	
Rubrica	Descrizione Interna		Didascalia talvolta apposta ai testi contenente ad es. il nome dell'autore o informazioni sul testo
Schema metrico	Descrizione Interna		
Schema rimico	Descrizione Interna		
Segnatura	Identificativo Univoco		
Stato di conservazione Condizione	Storia	<p>Alcune carte, o parti di esse, sono state da tempo ritagliate ed asportate: c. 1 (asportato l'intero foglio, ancora visibili tracce della iniziale nel margine superiore), cc. 20 e 21 (asportato tutto questo bifoglio centrale del fascicolo), c. 51 (margine inferiore), c. 85 (margine inferiore), c. 128r (margine inferiore), c. 147 (asportata l'intera carta). Presenza di cuciture originali su alcuni fogli (per es. c. 31, c. 145). Il codice è stato restaurato nel 1992-3 nel laboratorio di restauro di Andrea Giovannini a Lumino (v. Rapporto di restauro).</p>	<p>Conservazione del supporto Conservazione del tracciato e dei colori Conservazione del volume</p>
Supporto	Descrizione Esterna	pergamena	Materiale sul quale è stata tracciata la scrittura o che è destinato a riceverla (MM)
Testo	Descrizione Interna		

Tipo di scrittura	Descrizione Esterna	scrittura gotica corale	
Tipologia	Descrizione Interna		Prosa, Poesia, Prosimetro (nome temporaneo)
Titolo	Descrizione Interna		Se un titolo esiste nella tradizione
Titolo del codice	Descrizione Esterna	Codex Amiatinus	
Unità codicologica	Descrizione Esterna		VOLUME, parte di volume o insieme di volumi la cui esecuzione può essere conside-rata come un'operazione unica, realizzata nelle stesse condizioni di tecnica, di luo-go e di tempo
Versi per strofa	Descrizione Interna		
Versificazione Metro	Descrizione Interna		
Volume	Descrizione Esterna		Unità costituita da una serie di BIFOGLI o di FOGLI ricoperti o destinati ad essere rico-perti da una sola LEGATURA, a prescindere dal fatto che si tratti di un insieme costitu-to da una o più UNITÀ CODICOLOGICHE, indipendente o parte di un'opera in più volu-mi
Tavola	Descrizione Interna		Potrebbe essere, insieme a TESTO, una sottoclasse di CONTENUTO
Colophon/Sottoscrizio- ne	Descrizione Interna		
Filigrana	Descrizione Esterna		Caratteristica della Carta
Sigilli e timbri	Descrizione Esterna		TODO: legare alla STORIA (prob. Origine/Provenienza) esatto: vedi es. Palladio
Stemmi	Descrizione Esterna		TODO: legare alla STORIA (prob.

			Origine/Provenienza) esatto: vedi es. Palladio
Iniziali	Descrizione Esterna		

APPENDIX 1 (ENGLISH TRANSLATION):

Concept	Context	Examples	Definition
Addition / Insertion / Integration / Interpolation	Internal Description	fol. 152r outer margin: _hic introitus dicitur etiam in solemnitate corporis Christi._fol. 156v outer margin: _Introitus pro sanctissima trinitate quere in fine huius libri fo. 168._fol. 163r outer margin: <i>Require clxxv</i> , followed, in a later hand, by: <i>in libro sanctorum in die purificationis S. Marie virginis.</i>	A note written outside the <i>main body</i> of the page, intended to be inserted during reading or in a subsequent <i>copying</i> phase.
Annotation / Gloss / Note	Internal Description		A short text offering informative, explanatory, or critical content.
Page Architecture / Layout / Organisation / Utilisation of the Page	External Description		Overall arrangement of the various elements appearing on a <i>page</i> , according to specific principles and visual balance [M 331.01].
Activity	General		
Attribution in the Rubric	Internal Description		Author(s) as stated in the manuscript's rubric, if present.
Bibliography	History	Monti S., <i>L'esposizione di arte sacra in Bellinzona</i> (Sept 1903), in <i>Bollettino Storico</i>	

		<p>della Svizzera italiana 26 (1904), 17–18;[Respini G.], <i>Il Ticino liberale-conservatore giudicato dalle sue opere</i>, in <i>Bollettino Storico della Svizzera italiana</i>, 11 (1936), 87;</p>	
Bifolium / Leaf	External Description		<p>Constituent unit of a <i>quire</i>, consisting of a rectangular piece of <i>parchment, paper</i>, etc., folded in half to form two <i>leaves</i>.</p>
Leaf / Folio	External Description		<p>Each of the two halves of a <i>bifolium</i>.Note: The term <i>leaf</i> is sometimes used as a subunit of <i>bifolium</i>, to refer to each <i>folio</i>.</p>
Foliation / Leaf Numbering / Pagination	External Description		<p>Numbering of all the <i>leaves</i> making up a <i>volume</i>, usually written on the <i>recto</i> of each.</p>
Manuscript Circulation	Doubtful	<p>After the suppression of the convent of St Francis in Locarno (1848), the <i>gradual</i> (with Antiphonaries II, III, IV) was likely moved to the Madonna del Sasso convent in Orselina (run by Capuchins), where it was labelled “25–235 l”. By 1903, Monti saw it there, already missing some miniatures. Respini claimed early</p>	

		tampering occurred pre-1876. Further removals happened post-1943 and post-1967. Currently, the gradual and Antiphonaries II–IV belong to the Canton of Ticino and are held at the Capuchin convent, Madonna del Sasso, Orselina.	
Extent – Dimensions	External Description	I + 177 + II–III	Total number of <i>leaves</i> in a <i>volume</i> , regardless of how they are numbered (MM).
Content	Internal Description	Includes antiphonal and responsorial chants from Advent to the 23rd Sunday after Pentecost. fols. 2r–178v: <i>Proprium de Tempore</i> [Begins: <i>Dominica prima de Adventu</i> – beginning missing] 2r: <i>misericordiam tuam et salutare tuum da nobis. Offertorium. Ad te domine levavi animam meam</i> > <i>Dominica secunda de Adventu. Introitus. Populus Syon</i> ... to 178v: <i>Dominica XXIII post Pentecosten – officium resumitur de dominica preterita. Dicit dominus ego cogito et cetera</i> . Missing fols. 20–21 (parts of St Stephen and full St John the Baptist offices). Follows the <i>Ordo Breviarii</i> of	

		Haymo of Faversham, ed. S. P. J. Van Dijk, <i>Sources of the Modern Liturgy</i> (Leiden, 1963). fols. 123v–128r: Litanies (e.g., Francis, Anthony, Dominic, Clare). At fol. 125v: later additions of Saints Abbondio and Ludovico in the upper margin.	
Decoration	External Description	Initials retouched in yellow; rubrics and liturgical directions in red. Visible brown ink notations for rubricator and miniaturist; filigree initials:– small red and blue alternating at verse starts– medium-sized at Sunday and weekday mass openings. Attributed to a “Calligraphic Miniaturist” also active in Codices III and IV (Hudig-Frey 1971, p. 302, 318; Gilardoni 1972, p. 228; Speroni 2000, p. 42).	Overall arrangement of decorative elements on a <i>page</i> , observing particular principles and balance.
Edition	History		
Explicit	Internal Description		
Collation / Quire Structure	External Description	(IV–1)8 + IV16 + (IV–2)24 + 12 IV120 + V130 + IV138 + (IV–1)145 + (IV–1)154 + 3 IV178 + I180 + (II–2)182	a) Number and types of <i>quires</i> forming a <i>volume</i> or <i>codicological unit</i> . b) Study of <i>quire</i> types and structure in the volume.
Quire	External Description		Series of <i>bifolia</i> inserted into one

			another and stitched (or ready to be stitched) with a single thread pass. May also consist of a single <i>bifolium</i> or even one <i>leaf</i> , sewn individually.
Sheet	External Description		a) Rectangular surface of <i>parchment, paper</i> , etc. (equivalent to a <i>forme</i> sheet or whole skin, or part thereof), before folding or cutting into <i>bifolia</i> . b) Term used as synonym for <i>bifolium</i> . c) Term used as synonym for <i>leaf</i> .
Whole Sheet	External Description		Specific reference to meaning a) of <i>Sheet</i> .
Size – Format	External Description	528 × 375 mm	Height and width of a <i>sheet</i> or <i>leaf</i> .
Institution	General		
Event	General		
Collection / Archive / Fonds	History		
Genre in Rubric	Internal Description		
Textual Genre	Internal Description	Moral text, Religious text, etc.	
Illustration	Internal Description		Depiction of objects, figures, scenes, etc., in relation to the text.

Incipit	Internal Description		
Binding	External Description		a) Operation of assembling a <i>book</i> by sewing <i>quires</i> and possibly adding elements (cover, endbands, flyleaves, etc.).b) The result of such binding. Note: In this context, the term refers to sense b).
Language	Internal Description		
Place	General		
Place of Preservation	RELATION!		Place where the <i>book</i> is currently held.
Hand	External Description		
Manuscript	External Description		Any physical object bearing handwritten text.
Codex / Book / Volume	External Description		<i>Book</i> made of <i>leaves</i> folded in two (<i>bifolia</i>) and gathered into one or more <i>quires</i> , sewn with thread along the fold.
Marginalia	Internal Description		Notes added in the margin. Note: The term <i>manuscript</i> more generally refers to any handwritten text.

Miniature	Internal Description		Painted illustration in a <i>manuscript</i> , especially when it functions as a decorative or narrative <i>illustration</i> .
Musical Notation	Internal Description	Square notation in black ink on a red four-line staff	
Numbering	External Description		Order number assigned to the <i>quires</i> , <i>bifolia</i> , <i>leaves</i> , or <i>pages</i> of a <i>volume</i> .
Number of Strophes	Internal Description		
Number of Verses	Internal Description		
Origin	History	<p>Possibly the first of two volumes, the second intended to contain the <i>Proprium de sanctis</i> and the <i>Commune sanctorum</i>, as suggested by the reference at fol. 180v. Text follows the <i>Ordo</i> by Haymo of Faversham (Van Dijk ed., vol. II, 1963). Evidence for early 14th-century dating:– Addition of Saint Louis (canonised 1297) in the litanies (fol. 125v)– Feast of the Holy Trinity added at the end of the <i>Proprium de Tempore</i>, approved 1266, extended by Pope John XXII in 1316– Late note at fol. 130v (19th c.):</p>	Place where a <i>book</i> was produced

		_ Librum hunc...Anno 1315 Fr. Jacobus..._ – Initials in the Padua style of late 13th–early 14th century, e.g., Ms. 328 with “dragon motifs” (G. Abate – G. Luisetto, <i>Codici...</i> , 1975)	
Page	External Description		Each of the two sides of a <i>leaf</i> . Note: In modern terminology, “page” is sometimes used imprecisely to mean “leaf.”
Partition	Internal Description		For prose texts
Period	General		
Person	General		
Provenance	History	The <i>gradual</i> was likely produced for a Franciscan convent, intended for St Francis in Locarno (cf. litany with St Abbondio, Bishop of Como).Annotation at fol. 181r (19th c.): _Iste liber choralis...conventus Sancti Francisci...Anno 1817. _Statute at fol. 181 not evidence of local scriptorium (contra Hudig-Frey, Gilardoni, Speroni).Van Dijk found 9 manuscripts beginning with the same statute.Possible that in 1315 Fr. Giacomo di Rastelli Orelli and Fr.	a) Information about former <i>owners</i> or <i>_places of preservation_b)</i> Specifically: the last owner before the current one

		Giovanni Raimondi acquired the <i>gradual</i> and related antiphonaries (II–IV) for the convent at the time of its re-consecration in 1316 (cf. fol. 182v).	
Rubric	Internal Description		Heading sometimes indicating author or content of the text
Metrical Scheme	Internal Description		
Rhyme Scheme	Internal Description		
Shelfmark / Call Number	Unique Identifier		
Conservation Status / Condition	History	Losses from cutting/removal: fol. 1 (entire), fols. 20–21 (entire bifolium), fols. 51, 85, 128r, 147 (partial). Some leaves show original sewing (e.g., fols. 31, 145). Restoration performed in 1992–3 at Andrea Giovannini’s lab, Lumino (<i>Restoration Report</i>).	Conservation of support, script, colours, and structure
Writing Surface	External Description	Parchment	Material on which writing has been or will be inscribed (MM)
Text	Internal Description		
Script Type	External Description	Gothic rotunda script	

Type / Literary Form	Internal Description		Prose, Poetry, Prosimetrum (temporary label)
Title	Internal Description		If a title exists in the tradition
Codex Title	External Description	<i>Codex Amiatinus</i>	
Codicological Unit	External Description		A <i>volume</i> , part of a volume, or set of volumes considered as a single production event, made in the same technical, spatial, and temporal conditions
Lines per Stanza	Internal Description		
Versification / Metre	Internal Description		
Volume	External Description		A unit made up of <i>bifolia</i> or <i>leaves</i> , covered or meant to be covered by a single <i>binding</i> , regardless of whether it contains one or more <i>codicological units</i> , and whether stand-alone or part of a multi-volume work
Table	Internal Description		May be, along with <i>text</i> , a subclass of <i>content</i>
Colophon / Subscription	Internal Description		

Watermark	External Description		Characteristic of <i>paper</i>
Seals and Stamps	External Description		[To be linked to <i>History</i> – possibly <i>Origin/Provenance</i>]. See e.g., <i>Palladio</i>
Coats of Arms	External Description		[To be linked to <i>History</i> – possibly <i>Origin/Provenance</i>]. See e.g., <i>Palladio</i>
Initials	External Description		

APPENDIX 2

Soggetto	Relazione	Oggetto
Aggiunta	has	Descrizione
Architettura della pagina	has	Descrizione
Architettura della pagina	has	Tipo di scrittura
Carta	has	Cartulazione
Carta	Is composed by	Pagina
Circolazione del manoscritto	has	Data
Circolazione del manoscritto	has	Luogo
Circolazione del manoscritto	has	Persona
Codice	has	Fascicolazione
Codice	is composed by	Fascicolo
Codice	has	Legatura
Dimensioni	is represented by	Larghezza
Dimensioni	is represented by	Lunghezza
Dimensioni	has	Unità di misura
Ente	hosts	Attività
Ente	has	Descrizione
Ente	is_placed_in	Luogo
Ente	has	Vide
Evento	has	Descrizione
Evento	Happens in	Luogo
Evento	Has time span	Periodo
Fascicolo	has	Cartulazione

Fascicolo	has	Consistenza
Fascicolo	has datation	Data
Fascicolo	is composed by	Foglio
Fascicolo	has	Numerazione
Fascicolo	is made of	Supporto
Foglio	Is described by	Dimensioni
Foglio	has	Numerazione
Foglio	is made of	Supporto
Fondo	Is part of	Ente
Illustrazione	represents	Evento
Illustrazione	represents	Oggetto
Illustrazione	represents	Persona
Illustrazione	is related to	Testo
Luogo	has	Coordinate
Luogo	has	Descrizione
Luogo	has	Estensione
Mano	has	Collocazione nel manoscritto
Mano	has	Data
Mano	has	Tipo di scrittura
Manoscritto	has	Consistenza
Manoscritto	Is described by	Contenuto
Manoscritto	has datation	Data
Manoscritto	Is owned by	Ente
Manoscritto	is composed by	Foglio
Manoscritto	has	Nome vulgato
Manoscritto	Originated in	Origine
Manoscritto	Is owned by	Persona
Manoscritto	has been in	Provenienza
Manoscritto	is identified by	Segnatura
Manoscritto	has	Stato di conservazione
Manoscritto	consists of	Supporto
Manoscritto	transmits	Testo
Manoscritto	has title	Titolo del codice
Manoscritto	is composed by	Unità codicologica
Manoscritto	has	Bibliografia
Marginalia	carries	Annotazione
Marginalia	has	Descrizione
Origine	has	Ente
Origine	has	Persona
Pagina	includes	Aggiunta
Pagina	has	Annotazione

Pagina	Is described by	Architettura della pagina
Pagina	has	Cartulazione
Pagina	has	Decorazione
Pagina	contains	Illustrazione
Pagina	Is written by	Mano
Pagina	includes	Marginalia
Pagina	has	Numerazione
Pagina	contains	Notazione Musicale
Periodo	Begins in	Data
Periodo	Ends in	Data
Persona	Participates in	Attività
Persona	Is witness of	Evento
Persona	has	Morte
Persona	has	Nascita
Persona	has	Nome
Persona	Is active in	Periodo
Persona	has	Ruolo
Persona	has	Sesso
Persona	Is author of	Testo
Provenienza	has	Ente
Provenienza	has	Data
Rubrica	contains	Attribuzione in rubrica
Rubrica	contains	Genere in rubrica
Segnatura	Has prefix	Fondo
Segnatura	has	Segnatura numerica
Supporto	has	Materiale
Supporto	has	Stato di conservazione
Testo	has	Edizione
Testo	has	Explicit
Testo	is described by	Genere testuale
Testo	has	Incipit
Testo	Is written in	Lingua
Testo	is contained in	Pagina
Testo	is described by	Partizione
Testo	is authored by	Persona
Testo	contains	Rubrica
Testo	has	Tipologia
Testo	has	Titolo
Testo	is described by	Versificazione
Unità codicologica	has	Consistenza
Unità codicologica	is described by	Fascicolazione
Unità codicologica	is composed by	Fascicolo
Unità codicologica	is composed by	Foglio

Unità codicologica	has	Legatura
Versificazione	has	Numero strofe
Versificazione	has	Numero versi
Versificazione	has	Schema metrico
Versificazione	has	Schema rimico
Versificazione	has	Versi per strofa

APPENDIX 2 (ENGLISH TRANSLATION)

Subject	Relation Type	Object
Subject	Relation	Object
Addition	has	Description
Page Architecture	has	Description
Page Architecture	has	Script Type
Leaf	has	Foliation
Leaf	is composed of	Page
Manuscript Circulation	has	Date
Manuscript Circulation	has	Place
Manuscript Circulation	has	Person
Codex	has	Collation
Codex	is composed of	Quire
Codex	has	Binding
Dimensions	is represented by	Width

Dimensions	is represented by	Height
Dimensions	has	Unit of Measurement
Institution	hosts	Activity
Institution	has	Description
Institution	is located in	Place
Institution	has	Link
Event	has	Description
Event	takes place in	Place
Event	occurs during	Period
Quire	has	Foliation
Quire	has	Extent
Quire	has date	Date
Quire	is composed of	Sheet
Quire	has	Numbering
Quire	is made of	Writing Surface
Sheet	is described by	Dimensions
Sheet	has	Numbering
Sheet	is made of	Writing Surface

Collection/Fund	is part of	Institution
Illustration	depicts	Event
Illustration	depicts	Object
Illustration	depicts	Person
Illustration	is related to	Text
Place	has	Coordinates
Place	has	Description
Place	has	Area
Hand	has	Location in Manuscript
Hand	has	Date
Hand	has	Script Type
Manuscript	has	Extent
Manuscript	is described by	Content
Manuscript	has date	Date
Manuscript	is owned by	Institution
Manuscript	is composed of	Sheet
Manuscript	has	Common Title
Manuscript	originated in	Origin

Manuscript	is owned by	Person
Manuscript	has been in	Provenance
Manuscript	is identified by	Shelfmark
Manuscript	has	Conservation Status
Manuscript	consists of	Writing Surface
Manuscript	transmits	Text
Manuscript	has title	Codex Title
Manuscript	is composed of	Codicological Unit
Manuscript	has	Bibliography
Marginalia	carries	Annotation
Marginalia	has	Description
Origin	has	Institution
Origin	has	Person
Page	includes	Addition
Page	has	Annotation
Page	is described by	Page Architecture
Page	has	Foliation
Page	has	Decoration

Page	contains	Illustration
Page	is written by	Hand
Page	includes	Marginalia
Page	has	Numbering
Page	contains	Musical Notation
Period	begins in	Date
Period	ends in	Date
Person	participates in	Activity
Person	is witness to	Event
Person	has	Death
Person	has	Birth
Person	has	Name
Person	is active in	Period
Person	has	Role
Person	has	Gender
Person	is author of	Text
Provenance	has	Institution
Provenance	has	Date

Rubric	contains	Attribution in Rubric
Rubric	contains	Genre in Rubric
Shelfmark	has prefix	Collection/Fund
Shelfmark	has	Numeric Identifier
Writing Surface	has	Material
Writing Surface	has	Conservation Status
Text	has	Edition
Text	has	Explicit
Text	is described by	Textual Genre
Text	has	Incipit
Text	is written in	Language
Text	is contained in	Page
Text	is described by	Division
Text	is authored by	Person
Text	contains	Rubric
Text	has	Type
Text	has	Title
Text	is described by	Versification

Codicological Unit	has	Extent
Codicological Unit	is described by	Collation
Codicological Unit	is composed of	Quire
Codicological Unit	is composed of	Sheet
Codicological Unit	has	Binding
Versification	has	Number of Strophes
Versification	has	Number of Verses
Versification	has	Metrical Pattern
Versification	has	Rhyme Scheme
Versification	has	Verses per Strophe